

***DISTRIBUTION AND MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF SPECIES
BELONGING TO THE FAMILY OF LICHENS***

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Abstract: In this article, we will get to know in detail the representatives of the family of syrachadas, which are among the medicinal plants found in our nature. Together with this, we will get acquainted with their distribution, medicinal properties, growing conditions. There are 23 species in Central Asia. Since representatives of this family are unique and rare, 12 species are included in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The purpose of our study is to breed these species, to use their medicinal properties, and to widely apply them to the field of medicine.

Key words: Red Book, Central Asia, types of syrach, medicinal, syrach, perennial, botanical description, distribution, growing conditions.

Аннотация: В этой статье мы подробно познакомимся с представителями семейства сирачадовых, которые входят в число лекарственных растений, встречающихся в нашей природе. Вместе с этим мы познакомимся с их распространением, лечебными свойствами, условиями произрастания. В Средней Азии встречается 23 вида. Поскольку представители этого семейства уникальны и редки, 12 видов занесены в «Красную книгу» Республики Узбекистан. Цель нашего исследования — вывести эти виды, использовать их лечебные свойства и широко применить в области медицины.

Ключевые слова: Красная книга, Средняя Азия, виды сыра, лекарственный, сыра, многолетник, ботаническое описание, распространение, условия произрастания.

Introduction. Today, a lot of attention is being paid to our nature. The reason is to treat various diseases using natural plants in our medicine. They are also considered to be an invaluable asset of our nature. As long as we have plants, we breathe clean air and live. There are many medicinal plants, each of them has its own characteristics, many medicines have been created on the basis of our medicinal plants and are used in a number of diseases. Ladi. Almost all representatives of the family of shirachdoshadas are considered medicinal plants. There are 1,400-1,450 species of the Shirachdosh

family on earth, 61 species in the CIS, 45 species in Central Asia, and 23 species in Uzbekistan, 12 of which are included in the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Some of their species are cultivated, and representatives of the Aloe and Chlorophytum families are cultivated. Some species of representatives of this family are succulent species, that is, they store spare nutrients in their leaves and stems. The lychee plant occupies a special place in our nature. The lychee is one of our wild plants, which are beautiful, medicinal, and are eaten as greens. Let's get acquainted with some species of this family that are included in the "Red Book" and are common in nature.

History of access to science. Now the Asphodelaceae family has a complicated history, and its delimitation and taxonomy have varied greatly. In the 1981 Cronquist system, members of the Asphodelaceae were placed in the order Liliales. They struggled to classify this systematics. Therefore, the previous taxa were included in the single Liliaceae family, that is, the Asphodelaceae and Liliales orders. According to some information, the Dasypogonaceae family was included in the initial taxonomy. They were later removed from the Asphodelaceae because they belonged to the Comelinids. The decision to group the three previously separate families Asphodelaceae, Hemerocallidaceae and Xanthorrhoeaceae into a single family was first raised as a possibility in 2003. In 2017, the family Asphodelaceae was changed to a separate name. Today, the most famous and noteworthy among these taxonomists is the Asphodelaceae family.

Systematics:

Section: Magnoliophytes

Class: Liliopsida

Order: Amaryllidales

Family: Asphodelaceae

Type: Eremurus

General botanical definition: Shirach scientific name— EREMURUS. The genus Eremurus includes rhizome perennial herbs. The root is thickened, serete, the shapes are feathery, star-like. The rhizome is short. The stem is leafless and grows up to 3 meters tall. The leaves are pencil-shaped, linear-triangular, folded from the bottom, narrow or wide flat, three-sided and emerging from the root neck. As for the cauliflower, it is simple and has the shape of a flower. The flowers are 6-lobed, the petals of the flowers are white, pink, yellow, pale pink, and are located in two circles. The flowering time lasts for several months. The fruit is dark gray, light gray, spherical, swollen. The seeds are small and narrowly winged.

Eremurus is grown outdoors in flower beds. In the middle zone, the plant should not suffer from cold and moisture, it is appropriate if there are plants around it. We will achieve the desired result. Eremurus cannot tolerate high soil moisture, mainly it likes arid environment and is considered a plant adapted to such an environment. Adapted to grow mainly in soil rich in organic matter, does not like acidic soil. Eremurus rhizomes should be covered for better wintering. In order to grow it, we must first choose a place where there is a lot of sunlight. Eremurus is a plant that can withstand both high temperatures and extreme cold temperatures. It rarely requires regular watering. We also use several methods to reproduce it. In particular, it is propagated by means of vegetative and seeds. In autumn, when planting them in greenhouses, the temperature is 15-18 °C. Seedlings are ready in early spring. Seedlings are planted at a depth of 10 cm. Be careful when watering this plant, because too much water and moisture will cause its roots to rot.

Eremurus himalaicus is a very beautiful species of Himalayas north-east of Kashmir, it grows up to 1.2-2 meters in height and 60 cm in width. The leaves are arch-shaped, 30cm long and have a stem with a diameter of 2.5cm.

Eremurus spectabilis. A candle-shaped perennial plant, it is distributed in Turkey, Lebanon, Iran, Iraq and northern Pakistan. It grows up to 2 meters. The leaves are arch-shaped, gray-green in color, 30-40 cm long. Compared to other species, it blooms late, that is, it blooms in the middle of summer.

Eremurus x isabellinus. This species is known mainly by its *Eremurus olgae* and *Eremurus stenophullus* varieties. It grows up to 1.5 meters in length. Its width is up to 90 cm. There are several created varieties of this species, the leaves are spear-shaped, 15-30 cm long, the flowers are 2-3 cm in diameter, and the colors of the flowers are different. *Eremurus tauricus*. It is a perennial plant from Crimea, found in Yalta mountain forests, Crimean and Karadag reserves.

Eremurus robustus. It is a plant from Central Asia (Tianshan and Pamir mountains) with a height of 3 meters, leaves up to 1.2 meters long, and a stem up to 1.2 meters long. The color of the flowers is light pink, yellow, brown.

Eremurus algae. It differs from other species by the white-pink color of its flowers. The height is up to 1.5 meters.

Eremurus angustifolia. A species common in eastern countries, it grows in Central Asia, Iran and western Pakistan. Its height reaches only 1 meter. Its width is 60 cm. The leaves are gray-green, up to 24 cm long.

Eremurus alberti Regel. A perennial plant that reaches 25-80 cm in height. The rhizome is shortened, claw-like, the pieces are thickened like a scutellum, 7-10mm

thick. Shingles are sparse, many-flowered, 10-50 cm long. Petals have a large triangular, lance-shaped appearance.

Usefulness and healing. The flower of Eremurus is rich in honey, dried stems are used for bee boxes, young leaves and roots are boiled and eaten, rich in C medicinal drugs, i.e. vitamin C, carotene, organic acids, a large amount of eremuran polysaccharide, alkaloids and glue dyes are found. From ancient times, glue is extracted from its roots, and a dye is obtained from all its parts that dyes fabrics made of silk, wool, and cotton in a yellow color. Today, much attention is paid to this plant, because a polysaccharide called "eremuran" was found in its roots, and it is widely used in medicine. For example, the leaf is popularly used as a carminative, and the root is used as an expectorant for gastro-intestinal diseases. Today, a lot of attention is paid to this plant. Because a polysaccharide called "eremuran" was found in the root of eremurus, and it is used in medicine as an emulsifier that accelerates the absorption of many drugs into the body.

Spread. In our country, there are unique plants in every region, and all of them have their own area. All representatives of this family can be found in every region of our country. Eremurus alberti Regel is distributed in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions: Bobotog, Sherabad valley, around Dehkanabad and is also found in Tajikistan and Afghanistan. Eremurus iae Vved is also distributed in the Hisar range of the Surkhandarya region, in the Cho'lbayr mountains and in the northern part of Boysuntog. As for the Eremurus cow, it is mostly found in the Kurama mountain of the Tashkent region. Eremurus robustus Regel is one of the widespread representatives, mainly in Tashkent, Namangan, Jizzakh, Samarkand, Fergana, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya regions, in all the ranges of Western Tianshan and Pamir-Aloy, and also in neighboring countries, namely Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and It is also found in Kazakhstan. Another representative of the Republic of Uzbekistan included in the "Red Book" is Eremurus Nuratavicus. This species is widespread mainly in Jizzakh region and Nurota ridges.

Summary: The purpose of writing this article was to get to know the representatives of this family and study their characteristics. The purpose of my study was to practice breeding members of this family for their medicinal properties, as they are very useful. Representatives of Eremurus are considered to be a medicinal plant that can cure a number of ailments, as well as being a very beautiful sight. Having studied their distribution, it is also necessary to determine their habitat. Thanks to this, we can also grow them at home. Due to the decline of these species, several species

are included in the "Red Book" and are considered to be in need of protection. My conclusion is that this plant species is propagated and widely used in folk medicine.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qizil kitobi 2009.
2. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Qizil kitobi 2016.
3. Burxon, F., Enverovna, B. L., & Dilshod, M. (2024). CHAKANDA (HIPPOPHAE RHAMNOIDES) DORIVOR O'SIMLIGINING ZARARKUNANDALARI. *Science and innovation*, 3(Special Issue 21), 733-737.
4. Батиров, Х. Ф., Файзуллаев, Б., & Маликов, Д. (2022). ЗИМУЮЩИЕ ДВУЛЕТНИКИ В КАЧЕСТВЕ СИДЕРАТОВ. кандидат физико-математических наук, доцент ТН Ледащева Ч л е н ы р е д к о л л е г и и: доктор экономических наук, профессор ММ Редина; доктор геолого-минералдогических наук, профессор АП Хаустов; кандидат технических наук, профессор ЕВ Станис, 21, 311.
5. Burxon, F., & Dilshod, M. (2023). ZARAFSHON VOHASI SHAROITIDA TERAQ BARGHO 'RI CHRYSOMELA POPULI L. NING BIOLOGIK-EKOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI VA ZARARI. *PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION*, 19(23), 411-414.
6. Ruzikulova, D. X. (2024, May). YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES* (Vol. 1, No. 4, pp. 37-40).
7. Khasanova, F. (2020). The Role Of Baihua In Chinese Linguistics. *The American Journal of Interdisciplinary Innovations and Research*, 2(10), 97-102.
8. Ruzikulova, D., & Muminov, D. (2022). INSURANCE TECHNICAL RISKS AND CHALLENGES OF THEIR DEVELOPMENT. *Women's Health Medicine*, 18(1).
9. Khasanova, F. (2022). The Formation and Formation of The Chinese Language Baihua as The Basis of The Modern Chinese Language. *Sharq Mash'ali*, (01), 21-23.
10. Olim K. Khojimatov, Yusufjon Gafforov, Rainer W. Bussmann. 2023. Razm solish. Boshqa nashrlar.
11. Shirach; Tadjik: Khulika, Shirech; Kazakh: Shiryash; Kirghiz: Shiryash; English: Foxtail lily (Sokolov 1994). *Eremurus regelii* Vved.: Russian: Эремурус Регеля (*Eremurus Regelii*); Uzbek.
12. Nurillaev, J. Y. . (2021). Directions To Improve The Activities Of The Karakulchil Sector In Uzbekistan. *The American Journal of Interdisciplinary*

<https://doi.org/10.37547/tajjir/Volume03Issue02-11>

13. Yarashevich, P. N. J. (2023). Factors for Choosing a Marketing Strategy in Tourism Development.

14. Нуриллаев, Ж. Я. (1999). Оценка метафилактических мероприятий по отдаленным результатам хирургического лечения мочекаменной болезни у детей.

15. Karimov, A., & Khasanova, F. The Impact of Ancient Chinese on Baihua Language.

16. Nurillaev, J. Y. (2024). Theoretical and methodological foundations of financing karakul farming in a market economy.

17. Xolmanova, Z. (2022). SEMANTIK MAYDON VA SEMANTIK TO ‘R IMKONIYATLARI. COMPUTER LINGUISTICS: PROBLEMS, SOLUTIONS, PROSPECTS, 1(1).

